

Vulnerable Groups: Children, Asylum Seekers Refugees And Displaced Families In The Face Of Exploitation And Political Propaganda: The Use Of Migration Issues In The UK As A Political Gain Tool By British Politicians And Policy Makers In The UK

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Abstract

This paper explores how UK politicians use migration, particularly involving vulnerable groups such as children, asylum seekers, refugees, and displaced families, for political gain. By analysing the rise in non-EU migration from 2020 to 2023, and the political and media language surrounding it, the research shows how migration is framed as a threat or issue rather than a humanitarian issue affecting the world. This trend normally increases after a particular incident when there are serious concerns in public regarding the social cohesion of migrants which builds significant pressure on politicians or during election campaigns in order to convert sympathies¹ into electoral support. It argues that political rhetoric often increases discrimination and hate crime while failing to address the real root causes of migration. Using a Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) approach, the study examines how policies and campaign speeches contribute to negative outcomes for migrant communities in the UK and British society. It is noticed that politicians frame migration as the root cause of all sorts of mega-problems in order to enhance political support as well as justify discriminatory and strict policies against refugees. In addition, it is observed that there are different policies for migrants from different countries in the UK I-e that all migrants are not treated similarly.

Keywords: Migration, migrants, asylum seekers, refugees, immigration, discrimination against migrants, politics around migration in the UK.

1. Introduction

Migration has become one of the most debated hot issues in UK politics over the past few years due to both the social and political impact of UK policies. Rising global conflicts, economic instability, and humanitarian crises over the world have led to an increase in the number of people seeking safety and opportunity in the UK. Many of these individuals are vulnerable such as children, refugees, asylum seekers, and displaced families fleeing wars, persecution, or poverty from their homelands (Griffiths, 2022).

Instead of treating migration as a humanitarian responsibility, UK politicians often present it as a national security threat or economic and social issue in the UK. This is especially visible and clear during election campaigns, where promises to "control borders" or "reduce numbers" are used to attract voter support. Political language used in speeches and policies often focuses on fear, control, and division. As a result, migrants are frequently portrayed as threats rather than people in need or human beings seeking decent lives or opportunities.

This research examines how migration issues have been used as tools for political gain in the UK and challenges the current policies of treating migrants from different nationalities. It focuses on how vulnerable groups are affected by political messaging, public attitudes, and government policy. By analysing recent data, campaign speeches, and media coverage, the study aims to reveal how political interests can overshadow human suffering and create long-term harm for migrant communities in the UK especially those affected by wars and conflicts (Lomaxa, 2019).

In recent years, immigration in the UK has been increasingly politicised. Political parties in the UK, especially during election periods, have used migration as a tool to gain public support, trust and influence. This often includes negative messaging and harsh policies aimed at vulnerable migrants, including children and families. The result has been a rise in hate speech and crime, racial discrimination, and mental health issues among migrants. Instead of creating fair and humane solutions, the political focus on migration often deepens public fear and ignores the real suffering of those fleeing wars and conflicts.

Context and Background

In the past few years, the political conflicts in many nations around the world have driven the migration figures in the UK to rise in the past few years. Especially in the period from June 2020 and June 2023 when the migration figures started to rise across the UK by non-EU migrants with a sharp rise from 115,000 to 954,000. According to a Net Migration Report published in 2025 by the Migration Advisory Committee and the UK Home Office, the UK has been impacted by the rise of the migrants' figures in the past few years (Migration Advisory Committee, 2025). Therefore, there is a significant load of gigantic numbers of incoming international migrants on the public services in the UK. It is evident by recent Home Office statistics which show a significant increase in net migration between 2020 and 2023. As shown in Figure 1.2, UK net migration rose from approximately 111,000 to 906,000 (UK Government, 2025).

This increased migration made immigration not only a social and political issue but a central political talking point (Briggs, 2014).

Figure 1.2: UK net migration from 1964–2024 (UK Government, 2025)

The graph above shows how net migration, immigration, and emigration changed in the UK between 1964 and 2024.

Immigration means the number of people entering the UK to live and emigration is the number of people leaving the UK. Net migration is the difference between the number of people coming in and the number moving out.

Between the 1960s and the early 1990s, net migration was mostly low and sometimes negative, which means more people were leaving the UK than entering it. However, from

the late 1990s onwards, immigration began to rise steadily. Emigration also increased but at a slower rate.

A major shift happened after 2020 when net migration increased very sharply. This rise shows that many more people started coming to live in the UK than were leaving. Immigration levels reached over 1 million people per year during this time, while emigration remained lower (Lindley, 2024).

2. Literature Review

The Exploitation of Migration in the UK in Political Decision-making

This growing trend in migration has become a key area of focus for the current and recent British politicians and policymakers in the UK, who often raise the issue of immigration during election campaign periods. Migration is frequently used to attract voter attention and mobilise political support by promising to implement changes to the current migration system. These messages are often presented in political communication speeches, especially targeting citizens who do not necessarily belong to the far right but who may have growing concerns about migration and resettlement in Europe and the Western world (Goodfellow, 2020; Anderson, 2013). The rise of migration figures in the UK made it a gaining tool for the British politicians and people trying to gain public trust and power in the UK rather than a real opportunity to handle this humanity crisis affecting the world and the UK.

Immigration has thus become a powerful political tool. Politicians across various parties have been known to exploit public sentiment by using migrants especially vulnerable groups such as children, refugees, asylum seekers and displaced families as part of their narrative to justify stricter border controls and reduced asylum intake. These strategies often fuel fear and mistrust within the public and overshadow the humanitarian crises that force many individuals to migrate in the first place (Boswell, 2011; Cassidy, 2017) It is quite evident that how the British policymakers used migration issues in their political campaigns.

The Implications of Exploitation of Migration in Political Communication

This politicisation can distort the real experiences of migrants and may also result in hostile policies, such as the UK's "hostile environment" framework, which targets undocumented individuals but often impacts those legally residing in the country (Goodfellow, 2020). The use of migration issues in the UK and the political propaganda it creates could, lead to hate crimes, stalking and discrimination towards these vulnerable groups who have already been subject to the exploitation by wars, political conflicts and the political propaganda in the UK and many of them have already experienced the impact of extremism and the racism in their homelands. Furthermore, children and families seeking asylum can find themselves detained or placed in unsafe conditions due to these policies (Refugee Council, 2023). The youth could experience the biggest impact of these harmful and inhuman speeches that were used by the British political leaders who were trying to take advantage of these human issues in their political campaigns.

Political Campaign Examples (Case Study)

In the UK, migration and migrants have become one of the most common topics in political campaigns and among the British people themselves. British politicians often talk about immigration when they want to win public support, especially during elections. This section shows how both the Conservative Party and the Labour Party which are two of the UK's leading political parties in charge have used migration in their political campaigns.

As in the 2016 Brexit referendum, the Leave campaign used migration as one of the biggest reasons to leave the EU. Politicians from the “Leave” campaign often used migration as a major argument for leaving the European Union, linking it to economic pressure, loss of control, and cultural fear. A poster from UKIP, showing a long line of migrants with the words “Breaking Point,” was widely criticised. Many people said it was racist and made people feel afraid of migrants (BBC News, 2016). Even though this was not directly from the government, the message had a strong effect and helped start more negative views about migration and was a clear example of creating political propaganda about migration in the UK.

There was an image in which Nigel Farage, former UKIP leader, was standing in front of a large campaign poster that said "BREAKING POINT" and showed a long line of migrants. This image became a hot topic. The poster was used during the 2016 Brexit campaign by the Leave group to show that the UK had "lost control" of its borders.

Many people said this poster was racist and very dangerous while those from the right wing supported Nigel Farage's campaign. It used fear to make migration look like a big threat. The UK's equality watchdog termed it “offensive and irresponsible” (BBC News, 2016). The poster made it look like all migrants were the same and coming to the UK in large numbers, which was not true. The image had a strong effect on public opinion and helped create more fear and anger about immigration in the UK. And using pictures like this in political campaigns shows how powerful visuals can be in spreading negative messages about migrants. It is one of the most famous examples of migration being used as political propaganda in modern UK history.

More recently, from 2022 to 2023, because of the leadership race in the Conservative Party, Conservative leaders talked a lot about “stopping the boats.”; they made strong promises to stop the boats according to the recent ministers. They reduced asylum claims and asylum backlog which refers to the asylum seekers who were waiting for more than a year for their asylum claim. This referred to asylum seekers crossing the channel in small boats. This language was used to appeal to public fears and media pressure. However, asylum seekers, refugees and human rights groups argued that such rhetoric dehumanised asylum seekers and did not reflect international law or humanitarian responsibility (Amnesty International UK, 2022). These examples show that migration is often used not to inform the public, but to trigger emotional responses and gain political power and control over the country.

Politicians like recent PM Rishi Sunak and Suella Braverman (who was in charge of the home secretary) said they would reduce illegal migration and send some asylum seekers to Rwanda. Then her successor James Cleverly also after being appointed continued to support the same Rwanda plan which was started by Braverman. These plans received support from some voters but were criticised by human rights groups for being unfair and harmful to refugees (Amnesty International UK, 2022). These plans were also used as a strong indication to the public who were supporting the party to gain their support and trust.

The Labour Party has also addressed migration but with a different approach. In recent years, Labour leaders criticised the Conservative government's handling of immigration, claiming it was chaotic and lacked control. They promised to create a fairer and better-managed system.

After becoming prime minister, Keir Starmer made significant changes to Labour's immigration policy. On 13 May 2025, he delivered a speech introducing a new immigration plan. Starmer stated that the UK risked becoming an "island of strangers" without stricter immigration controls. He emphasised the need to "take back control" of the borders and proposed measures such as increasing the time required to gain permanent residency from five to ten years, raising English language requirements for all visa applicants, restricting

visas for low-skilled workers, including those in the care sector and prioritising high skilled migrants and those contributing significantly to society (Somerville, 2021).

Starmer's speech aimed to balance the need for immigration control with the recognition of migrants' contributions to the UK. However, some critics compared his language to that of past controversial figures, arguing that it could fuel negative sentiments towards migrants, asylum seekers and refugees.

These examples explain how both major UK political parties use migration as a campaign topic, albeit with different strategies. The Conservatives often focus on control and security, while Labour emphasises fairness and planning. Nonetheless, both parties aim to influence public opinion and gain support by addressing immigration, highlighting its significance in UK politics and decision-making (Hatton, 1999).

Anti-Immigration Riots and Public Unrest

In the summer of 2024, the UK experienced significant unrest related to immigration. These events were comprised of severe violence and hate crimes against migrants. These events illustrate how migration issues can be exploited in political debates as well as the impact of this exploitation on society.

Between July 30 and August 7, 2024, there were approximately 29 anti-immigration demonstrations and riots across 27 towns and cities in the UK. These events were marked by violence, including attacks on mosques and hostels housing asylum seekers. Far-right activists promoted and participated in these riots, spreading misinformation online that fuelled anger.

A tragic incident in Southport, England where three young girls were killed, was falsely linked to an Islamist migrant by online rumours. This misinformation led to widespread unrest all over the UK. It highlighted the dangers of fake news in influencing public opinion and inciting violence (Phillimore, 2021).

Impact on Migrants and Public Perception

The combination of violent protests, policy changes, and political rhetoric had a significant impact on migrants in the UK. Many asylum seekers reported increased fear, anxiety, and a sense of isolation. The Mental Health Foundation noted a deterioration in mental health among asylum seekers following the summer riots including the hardships and trauma they are already facing.

Public opinion was also affected. A YouGov survey indicated that immigration became the top concern for UK residents after the riots, reflecting the influence of political discourse and media coverage on public attitudes in the UK. The 2024 large-scale summer riots after the Southport incident in the UK show the impact of inappropriate media coverage, such as deliberately linking the migrants with it (Mulcaire, 2024).

Therefore, use of negative language in political speeches does not only affect public opinion it also affects the mental health and well-being of migrants as human beings who could feel the fear and the negative impact of the political language British policymakers are using when talking about migration. Refugees and asylum seekers, especially children, are already dealing with trauma from war, displacement and loss. When they are treated as political problems rather than people, they may face more isolation, fear, and discrimination in the UK.

According to the UK Refugee Council (2023), many young asylum seekers in the UK suffer from anxiety, depression, and loneliness because of the way they are treated by both the

system and the media. Some face poor living conditions, long delays in asylum decision-making processes by the UK Home Office and the fear of deportation. These stresses have led to serious mental health crises.

A notable example was in 2020 when a Syrian refugee boy named Rasoul Iran Nejad drowned in the English Channel with his family while trying to reach the UK. His case shows how dangerous and desperate refugee journeys can be, especially when safe legal routes are limited to certain countries (The Guardian, 2020). In another case, a young asylum seeker known as Alexander committed suicide in a UK hotel in 2022 while waiting for a decision on his asylum claim (BBC News, 2022). Campaigners said he had lost hope after being left in oblivion for months with no clear support which is another example of how the exploitation of human suffering in politics can lead to inhuman treatment.

A project 'Amal' was launched to raise awareness regarding this issue.

A giant puppet representing a 10-year-old Syrian refugee girl who travelled across Europe was created to raise awareness of the emotional experiences of child refugees without family or relatives. The project aimed to show the world the loneliness, fear, and resilience of children forced to leave their homes (Good Chance Theatre, 2021). These examples show that political messaging is not just words it can directly affect how migrants are treated and how they feel about themselves, their future, and their place in British society.

Special Support for Ukrainian Refugees

In recent years, the UK has welcomed some refugees with open arms, while making it much harder for others to get help; the amount of support delivered to some was completely different from others. The way migrants are treated in the UK often depends on where they come from, rather than what they are going through. This part of the research explains how the UK gave support to some people, like those from Ukraine, but made it difficult for others to escape conflicts in Africa, the Middle East, Asia and other parts of the world where there are political conflicts and wars (Asif, 2022).

After Russia invaded Ukraine in February 2022, the UK quickly introduced safe routes for Ukrainian people to enter the country. The Ukraine Family Scheme and Homes for Ukraine programme allowed thousands of Ukrainian refugees to come legally and live with host families or relatives in the UK. These schemes also gave access to schools, and healthcare, and gave the right to work and all the other civil rights the British citizens have (UK Government, 2022).

This shows that when the UK government wants to help, it can act fast and show strong compassion. Politicians praised this policy as a way to protect freedom and support victims of war and political conflicts. Although this support is positive, it highlights double standards in immigration policy. If the UK can organise quick, safe help for Ukrainians, why is it so hard for people from other countries in crisis to get the same help?

Unequal Treatment of Refugees and Human Suffering in UK Immigration Policy

Refugees fleeing wars and violence in other parts of the world have not received the same support. Many people from African, Middle-Eastern, and Asian countries are treated very differently.

Instead of safe visa routes, many of these refugees take dangerous journeys to reach the UK. If they arrive in small boats, they may be detained or sent to Rwanda under government plans (Amnesty International UK, 2022). Others wait in hostels or detention centres with no clear updates for months or years and some of these life seekers are losing hope and, in some cases, some asylum seekers commit suicide because of neglect.

This shows that the UK chooses who to support based on politics and geography, not just human needs or according to the international refugee agreement that was crafted in Geneva which was assigned by the UK in July 1951. The convention was made to define the refugee and their rights, Even though people from Libya, Sudan or Yemen may be in danger, they are not given the same level of protection as Ukrainians. The policy difference creates a message that some lives matter more than others. This can increase racism and discrimination, and it damages the UK's image as a fair country that supports human rights and people escaping countries where there is political conflict or civil war (Murray, 2013).

In Palestine, especially in Gaza and the West Bank, people have been living in conflict for many years. The recent rise in violence has made the situation worse, with thousands killed or displaced. However, the UK has not offered a similar visa scheme or a clear support plan for Palestinians (The Guardian, 2024). Palestinians escaping war and trauma have very few legal ways to come to the UK, even when facing bombs, poverty and scarcity of food every day on everyone's watch. This shows a lack of consistency in UK foreign policy. It suggests that some refugees are ignored because of political alliances or fear of criticism from certain political groups. The tragedy happening today in Gaza is a clear example of the global community's biggest failures to support people who were left behind in war.

Ukrainian refugees were offered free housing, English language classes, mental health support and access to the NHS and schools. In contrast, many Libyans, Sudanese, Eritrean, Yemeni or Afghan asylum seekers are stuck in oblivion. They live in overcrowded hostels, do not get mental health support, and wait a long time for decisions (Refugee Council, 2023). This creates inequality in how the UK supports people in need. These differences are not only unfair they go against the idea that all people have the right to safety and dignity. A refugee's country of origin should not decide how well they are treated. Fairness in accessibility to public services must apply to all, especially to groups of people who are in the same situation and come from places where there is a political conflict or war and human suffering.

The UK has shown that it is capable of helping refugees however it does not help everyone equally. People from countries like Ukraine are welcomed and supported, while others from Africa, the Middle East, or Asia are often ignored, delayed or sent away. This creates an unfair refugee system, which reflects political interests based on borders and geography rather than human needs or real solutions to end humanity's crisis (Kaufman, 2022).

Recommendations

There are several recommendations and measures by human rights groups or non-profit organisations that work closely with these vulnerable groups. These organisations have been pushing and encouraging policymakers in the UK to implement changes.

The measures and recommendations of this research focus on political communication and not using migration as a political support-gaining tool in the UK. It is required to promote fair and balanced political speech; politicians should avoid using harmful language when talking about migration. Instead, public debates should include real stories from migrants and facts about the causes of migration (Turcatti, 2024). Protect vulnerable groups such as children, families, and asylum seekers. They should be treated with dignity as human beings rather than a defined threat from their point of view. The UK government should stop placing children in detention or unsafe housing especially those without family or relatives seeking opportunities in the UK.

It is required to educate the public regarding the difference between legal asylum-seeking and illegal immigration, and why people flee their home countries by means of awareness campaigns.-Support integration and funding should be provided for language education, housing support, and mental health services to help new arrivals feel welcome and safe.

3. Research Methodology:

This research uses a qualitative method. In this type of research, the information is assembled in narrative instead of quantifiable outcomes like a transcript of an unstructured detailed interview or speech. The objective of this research approach is to develop concepts which assist in clarifying facts in a natural environment instead of an experimental one, providing a needed focus on opinions and meanings (Verhoef, 1997). The aim is to understand how UK politicians and policymakers exploit migration for their political gains. They carry out speeches on different occasions, especially during elections in order to target vulnerable groups like children, refugees, asylum seekers and displaced families for political purposes to get support from groups and communities which are against migration. The study is based on secondary data. Therefore, it will be based on different digital resources which are available online such as reports, books, journals, conference papers, news articles, and some published government documents.

This research will employ Critical Discourse Analysis in order to meet the objectives of this paper. The current research paper explores how lexical depiction, development of phrases, and coherency in speeches in a specific socio-political context with certain beliefs impact the perception of people (Datondji, 2019). The contribution of the author is to analyse the textual approaches and explain the relational, eloquent, and indicative values in the speeches of politicians of the UK by focusing on broader social-political viewpoints (Breeze, 2011). The current research enhances the existing literature by carrying out analysis of selected speeches of UK politicians related to migration based on choices of words, digressive practices and socio-political viewpoints. In addition, this research focuses on how particular lingual organisations allow the speaker to communicate his/her convictions in an effective manner and drive the audience to receive their support wholeheartedly.

Data Collection

The information used in this research comes from:

- Public speeches
- Parliamentary Discussions
- Interviews made by existing organisations
- Articles (written by politicians or quoted them)

The data is gathered from multiple speeches of UK politicians from year 2000 to 2005. A total of 10 speeches are selected comprising both Labour Party and Conservative Party politicians in order to analyse their stance on migration. These political figures include Suella Braverman, David Cameron, Theresa May, Keir Starmer, Tony Blair, William Hague, Rishi Sunak, Boris Johnson and Priti Patel.

The selected speeches of the above-mentioned political figures are:

- Suella Braverman (Former Home Secretary) carried out a speech in 2021 in which she criticised migration.
- Former Prime Minister David Cameron passed indecent remarks regarding immigrants in his speech in 2015 as Prime Minister.
- Former Prime Minister Theresa May carried out a speech in 2013 in which she gave a statement in which she stated that strict actions will be taken so that migrants cannot stay here in the UK.

- Prime Minister Keir Starmer carried out a speech in 2024 in which he termed migration as a reason for inadequate wages and housing.
- Former Prime Minister Tony Blair carried out a speech in 2000 in which he showed intentions to tighten border controls.
- William Hague (Member of Conservative Party) carried out a speech in 2000. He stated migration is impacting national identity.
- Former Prime Minister Rishi Sunak carried out a speech in 2023 as Prime Minister in which he stated to launch a national emergency to stop migration.
- Former Prime Minister Boris Johnson carried out a speech in 2022 as Prime Minister in which he favoured the migration of Ukrainians.
- Priti Patel (Former Foreign Secretary) passed insensitive and derogatory remarks regarding migrants while presenting the bill in parliament in 2021. In addition, she gave another speech in 2022 relevant to Ukraine's migrants in parliament.

This data was collected between the years 2020 and 2025, focusing on the period when migration became a major issue in UK politics.

Method of Analysis

The research uses a method called Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). CDA is employed in order to explore how language is used in speeches, reports, and news stories. The goal is to investigate how politicians talk about migrants and why. This helps in showing how migration is sometimes used to create fear or gain support during elections. For carrying out Critical Discourse Analysis, the model suggested by Norman Fairclough (1992) is followed. There are three aspects of this framework in order to analyse any discussion or text. It is comprised of text analysis, socio-cultural conventions and digressive practices. Text is analysable as social, economic, and political impact the digressive practices have in societal settings (Fairclough, 1992).

Fairclough (1989) explained the goal of this framework as a participation in the generic enhancement of awareness of exploitation in society by means of paying attention to language. The theoretical framework of this research paper is CDA (Fairclough, 1989). This framework assesses the discourses in a critical manner and uncovers the social practices such as supremacy, persecution and exploitation of unprivileged people. It is the intersection of two domains such as social sciences and linguistics. This analysis is based on parameter I-e language in order to investigate the discussion exhibits digressive practices in a society (Sipra, 2013). This research paper's subject is related to the exploitation of migration by UK politicians is primarily dealt with by CDA. This subject incorporates variables such as social and political disparity and beliefs which are the main problems analysed by Critical Discourse Analysis. In this paper, it is investigated how migrants are being described in political speech, and how migration is used as "the biggest issue or threat" in campaigns. The current theoretical model provides a full foundation for the analysis of variables in the speeches.

Ethical Considerations

Research ethics are abided by the author of this research. This study only uses publicly available documents in a fair and transparent manner. As the current work has a qualitative nature so does not include interviews or personal data. Therefore, this methodological approach does not lead to ethical issues. Because of this, no ethical approval is needed. Still, care is taken to write about vulnerable people like children, asylum seekers and refugees with respect and accuracy.

CDA framework is employed to carry out this research. The type of research is completely qualitative as analysis of different speeches is carried out based on the framework of Fairclough. Critical Discourse Analysis is adopted as a methodology with a wider scope for analysing speeches of UK politicians (Zhang, 2020).

Limitations

This research only looks at written texts and public data. It does not include interviews with migrants or people affected by these policies which is the next biggest goal of this research to be impactful research rather than presenting findings and information supported by evidence. Also, some of the sources like political speeches or media articles may be biased, so they are carefully analysed and considered.

4. Findings

The data is assembled from speeches of 9 political figures of the UK who served in different senior positions including the Premiership. These senior politicians including Suella Braverman, David Cameron, Theresa May, Keir Starmer, Tony Blair, William Hague, Rishi Sunak, Boris Johnson and Priti Patel carried out speeches regarding migration and portrayed it as an issue for the UK.

The relevant sentences of these speeches are analysed as well as elucidated by means of a framework devised by Fairclough which is regarding values related to expressions, inter-relations, and ideas. This framework assesses the complete text based on three facets in a wider threshold, that are relevant to analysing text, and discourse practices in the backdrop of that specific chunks of texts considering specifically social, financial and political components.

As mentioned above, this research is based on Critical Discourse Analysis as a conceptual model as it emphasises content which shows social inequity, racial bias, and other social issues by analysing content from a socio-political lens. The nature of this research is explanatory. Initially, this framework highlights all aspects by providing an explanation of lingual attributes employed in these specific speeches. Furthermore, it attempts to translate the connection of the relevant pieces of content with the interaction. Moreover, it describes the relation of interaction with wider social and political variables.

Labelling Migrants as a National Security Threat

Text Analysis

Migration is perceived in the context of national security. In 2022, Suella Braverman explained the entry of migrants by means of the Channel as an “invasion on our southern coast” (Morton, 2022).

Likewise, then-PM David Cameron mentioned the people who are migrating through the Mediterranean as a “swarm” (BBC, 2015). They used two metaphors. Suella Braverman used “invasion” which is employed to give the perception of militant invasion. David Cameron used “swarm” which is employed in dehumanising people. The choices of these words indicate that migrants are a group of people who are threatening the British and eroding their national identity. The verbs employed such as “must” and “will” exhibit assertion and priority.

Discourse Practice

These speeches are carried out at significant events. Moreover, these are published by big media houses including BBC and The Guardian for public consumption. These speeches are repeated over and over again on major channels as political messages for achieving objectives during different times including election campaigns.

Socio-Political Context

Migration is framed as a national security issue as people have growing concerns after Brexit and during high international migration. By means of such framing, they validate strict border controls. It assists politicians in gaining popularity as well as electoral support.

Perceiving Migrants as Financial Burden

Text Analysis

Migration is framed as a burden on the economy as well as public services. In 2013, Theresa May said that immigrants who are not legal “have no right to be here, and we will make it harder for them to remain” (Travis, 2013). It is strengthening expulsion by means of legalist and ethical assertions.

Similarly, Keir Starmer admitted that a high number of migrants “under a broken system” had a greater impact on housing as well as remuneration (Syal, 2024). This sort of statement is posturing migrants as the sole reason for unemployment and inadequate public service delivery.

Discourse Practice

These sorts of arguments are intentionally incorporated in policy speeches so they can be shared in different newspapers and channels in order to align the party’s policy and manifesto with financial matters. It is carried out while targeting swing voters or the working class.

Socio-Political Context

There is a significant increase in living costs in the UK. Likewise, the wages are stagnant. In addition, there is a serious housing crisis. Politicians frame migration as a reason for these issues. Therefore, they give justifications for limited access to benefits, social housing and working rights to people who migrated.

Identity-related Concerns

Text Analysis

In some political circles, there are concerns regarding the UK’s national identity and they have the perception that immigration is the reason behind this national identity crisis. In 2005, Tony Blair justified the strict border controls. He stated that “we need rules that are fair, but also firm” (The Guardian, 2005). However, in addition to this, he wanted unity and social inclusion. His stance exhibited that migrants are a major hurdle in social cohesion unless they are appropriately controlled.

Likewise, in 2000, William Hague in a speech informed that the asylum system of the UK was “close to breakdown”. He blamed the Labour Party’s government of that time for this national identity crisis (The Guardian, 2000). It can be implied that it is a hindrance to social unity.

Discourse Practice

Tony Blair and William Hague carried out speeches in the environment of elections and discussions related to inclusiveness. It seems like consensus efforts to get public support especially related to immigration. These speeches are carried out after the incident of 9/11 or in the wake of big rampages which causes concerns about cohesion.

Socio-Political Context

In the early years of 2000, there was political discussion on a national scale regarding migration and how it is fragmenting the culture. There was immense public pressure on

these political actors. This is why they positioned migration in such a way in order to justify tests for nationality and language requirements. These policies allowed them to discriminate against migrants on the basis of their race.

Framing and Declaring Emergency

Text Analysis

The rhetoric of politicians gives the perception that migration is a problem which requires to be resolved. In 2023, Rishi Sunak launched a campaign “Stop the Boats” (Sandford, 2023). As per this campaign, there was a national emergency at that time as boats cross borders. This campaign reiterated there are no controls on borders.

In a similar manner, in 2021, Priti Patel in her speech for the Nationality and Borders Bill passed indecent remarks against migration and criticised the asylum system. She stated that this system’s loopholes were being “exploited by criminal gangs” and was “collapsing under pressure.”. She framed that migration is exploiting the system so it is an emergency situation (GOV.UK, 2021).

Discourse Practice

These narratives are propagated through major media outlets in order to resonate broadly. Such media campaigns increase the moral panic environment.

Socio-Political Context

Such sort of public discussions are carried out during legislations like the Nationality and Borders Bill. Positioning it as an emergency allows them to sell the rhetoric in public effectively. Moreover, it allows to avoid criticism, decrease sympathy in people, and positions actions to safeguard migrants as shortcomings which are being misused.

Humanitarian Positioning

Text Analysis

In 2022, Boris Johnson stated that the United Kingdom’s “unwavering support for Ukraine”. Moreover, he launched a project for Ukrainians “Homes for Ukraine” (GOV.UK, 2022).

Moreover, in 2022, Priti Patel gave a speech relevant to Ukraine’s migrants in parliament. She stated in a statement that the UK “desire to help as many people as possible” (GOV.UK, 2022).

Discourse Practice

These speeches are shared across mainstream channels, giving the perception that the UK is a magnanimous country which is accommodating the people of a country which is going through a war crisis.

Socio-Political Context

This treatment of the UK with Ukraine’s refugees is in severe contrast to the way the UK treats migrants who belong to other countries including Middle Eastern countries and African countries. UK welcomed European Christians while others were dehumanised.

5. Conclusion

This research showed that migration is not just a policy topic it is also used as a political support-gaining tool in the UK by the British Politicians. Politicians often speak about migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers in ways that create fear or win votes. Sadly, this causes more suffering for vulnerable people who are already escaping war, poverty, and dangerous conditions.

By using Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), this research looked at how political speeches, campaign messages, and government reports describe migrants. The language often shows bias, fear, or blame. This kind of language impacts the opinions of the public and how policies are made.

The research also found that not all refugees are treated equally. Ukrainians received faster help, better services, and more support. But people from other Middle Eastern and African countries face delays, poor housing, or deportation threats. This shows the UK has an unfair refugee system based more on politics than on fairness or human need.

The information used here highlights how the UK needs a more fair, honest, and respectful way to speak about migration and support migrants. British decision-makers and policymakers must stop using migration as a way to gain power. Real people's lives are affected, and their human rights should be the top priority as well as filtering migration and creating a more inclusive system that supports all people in need especially those affected by war and conflict.

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